

KEY DRIVERS OF WILDFIRE OCCURRENCE IN THE MARROMEU COMPLEX, MOZAMBIQUE: INSIGHTS FROM REMOTE SENSING AND GEOSPATIAL ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

Objective: This study aims to identify the key factors driving fire occurrence in the Marromeu Complex (Mozambique) and to assess the extent to which each environmental, topographic, socio-economic, and vegetation-related variable influences fire frequency.

Theoretical Framework: The research is based on fire ecology and landscape ecology, highlighting interactions between climatic variability, vegetation structure, anthropogenic pressures, and topographic factors. Models for fire regime characterization and vulnerability assessment underpin the analysis.

Methods: A quantitative approach integrated climatic (temperature, humidity, precipitation), topographic (altitude, slope, solar exposure), land cover, and socio-economic variables (vegetation cover, population density and roads). A statistical modeling framework was applied, explaining 97.8% of fire frequency variation.

Results and Discussion: Vegetation cover was the primary driver of fire occurrence, with higher incidence in less dense areas. Temperature, precipitation, population density, and proximity to roads further shaped fire dynamics, while elevation and slope modulated fire spread. Residual variability (2.2%) indicates additional unaccounted drivers.

Research Implications: Findings support fire management, risk mitigation, and land-use planning, providing a scientific basis for conservation strategies in tropical ecosystems such as the Marromeu Complex.

Originality/Value: The study advances fire regime research by integrating environmental and socio-economic variables in a tropical wetland context. It offers novel insights for conservation management in data-scarce African regions.

Keywords: Fire regime, Marromeu Complex, Vegetation cover, Climatic variability, Fire ecology.

FATORES DETERMINANTES DE INCÊNDIOS FLORESTAIS NO COMPLEXO MARROMEU, MOÇAMBIQUE: CONTRIBUIÇÕES DO SENSORIAMENTO REMOTO E DA ANÁLISE GEOESPACIAL

RESUMO

Objetivo: Este estudo tem como objetivo identificar os principais fatores que determinam a ocorrência de incêndios no Complexo Marromeu (Moçambique) e avaliar a extensão em que cada variável ambiental, topográfica, socioeconômica influencia a frequência de incêndios.

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Referencial Teórico: A pesquisa baseia-se na ecologia do fogo e na ecologia da paisagem, destacando as interações entre variabilidade climática, estrutura da vegetação, pressões antrópicas e fatores topográficos. Modelos para caracterização do regime de incêndios e avaliação de vulnerabilidade sustentam a análise.

Métodos: Foi adotada uma abordagem quantitativa que integrou variáveis climáticas (temperatura, umidade, precipitação), topográficas (altitude, declividade, exposição solar), de cobertura do solo e socioeconômicas (cobertura vegetal, densidade populacional e rodovias). Aplicou-se modelo estatístico para explicar a variabilidade nas variáveis.

Resultados e Discussão: A cobertura vegetal foi o principal determinante da ocorrência de incêndios, com maior incidência em áreas menos densamente vegetadas. Temperatura, precipitação, densidade populacional e proximidade a rodovias também influenciaram a dinâmica do fogo, enquanto altitude e declividade modulavam a propagação. O modelo que explicou 97,8% da variação na frequência de incêndios.

Implicações da Pesquisa: Os achados oferecem suporte à gestão de incêndios, mitigação de riscos e planejamento do uso do solo, fornecendo uma base científica para estratégias de conservação em ecossistemas tropicais, como o Complexo Marromeu.

Originalidade/Valor: O estudo avança na compreensão do regime de incêndios integrando variáveis ambientais e socioeconômicas em um contexto de zonas úmidas tropicais. Ele fornece novos insights para a gestão da conservação em regiões africanas com escassez de dados.

Palavras-chave: Regime de fogo, Complexo de Marromeu, Cobertura vegetal, Variabilidade climática, Ecologia do fogo.

FACTORES CLAVE DE LA OCURRENCIA DE INCENDIOS EN EL COMPLEJO MARROMEU, MOZAMBIQUE: PERSPECTIVAS DESDE EL ANÁLISIS GEOESPACIAL Y EL SENSORIAMIENTO REMOTO

RESUMEN

Objetivo: Este estudio busca identificar los factores clave que determinan la ocurrencia de incendios en el Complejo Marromeu (Mozambique) y evaluar la influencia de variables ambientales, topográficas y socioeconómicas en la frecuencia de incendios.

Marco Teórico: La investigación se fundamenta en la ecología del fuego y del paisaje, destacando cómo la variabilidad climática, la estructura de la vegetación, las presiones humanas y los factores topográficos interactúan para moldear el régimen de incendios.

Métodos: Se aplicó un enfoque cuantitativo integrando variables climáticas (temperatura, humedad, precipitación), topográficas (altitud, pendiente, exposición solar), de cobertura del suelo y socioeconómicas (cobertura vegetal, densidad poblacional y proximidad a carreteras). Se empleó un modelo estadístico lineal que explicó la mayor parte de la variabilidad observada en la frecuencia de incendios.

Resultados y Discusión: La cobertura vegetal fue el principal factor que determinó la ocurrencia de incendios, con mayor incidencia en áreas menos densas. La temperatura aumentó la frecuencia de fuego, mientras que la precipitación tuvo efecto inverso. La densidad poblacional y la proximidad a carreteras incrementaron el riesgo de ignición, y altitud y pendiente modulaban la propagación. El modelo explicó el 97,8% de la variabilidad observada.

Implicaciones: Los hallazgos proporcionan base científica para la gestión de incendios, mitigación de riesgos y planificación del uso del suelo en ecosistemas tropicales.

Originalidad/Valor: El estudio integra variables ambientales y socioeconómicas en un contexto de humedales, ofreciendo información valiosa para estrategias de conservación en regiones africanas con escasez de datos.

Palabras clave: Régimen de fuego; Complejo de Marromeu; Cobertura de la vegetación; Variabilidad climática; Ecología del fuego.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Wildfires are both a natural phenomenon and an essential ecological process that, over millions of years, have shaped landscapes and sustained biodiversity (Bowman et al., 2013). However, in recent decades, anthropogenic drivers, such as land-use and land-cover change, climate change, and population growth, have intensified the frequency and severity of these events in many regions worldwide (Syphard et al., 2007). It is estimated that, in Africa alone, more than two million hectares are affected annually by wildfires (Archibald et al., 2010).

Mozambique is among the countries in Southern Africa that still preserve extensive tracts of native forests and other woody formations, predominantly composed of Miombo, Mecrusse, and Mopane ecosystems. These dry tropical forests are ecologically fragile and highly vulnerable to degradation and deforestation, driven by increasing resource demand and the dependence of rural populations (FAO, 2020; Boanha & Madeira, 2025). The country ranks among the most wildfire-affected nations in the region, with annual forest loss of approximately 267,000 ha (World Bank, 2018; MITADER, 2018) and over 50% of its territory burned each year, placing it among the top three countries with the highest burning rates in Southern Africa (Archibald et al., 2010).

The Marromeu Complex covers approximately 1.5 million hectares and encompasses a wide range of ecosystems, including wetlands, forests, savannas, floodplains, mangroves, and lacustrine margins. This ecological heterogeneity makes it a biodiversity hotspot, hosting threatened species such as the African elephant (*Loxodonta africana*) and the African wild dog (*Lycaon pictus*) (Beilfuss, Bento, & da Silva, 2010). Recognizing its importance, the Government of Mozambique ratified the Ramsar Convention in 2003, designating the Marromeu Complex as the country's first Wetland of International Importance (Pritchard, Bamba, & Rilla, 2009). Furthermore, since 1982, the area has been recognized by UNESCO as a Biosphere Reserve.

Despite its protected status and ecological significance, the Marromeu Complex has been heavily impacted by fires, predominantly of anthropogenic origin, linked to activities such as illegal hunting and fishing, agriculture, charcoal production, cigarette disposal, and the expansion of human settlements (Beilfuss, Bento, & da Silva, 2010). Between 2002 and 2019,

approximately 12,227 fire hotspots were detected, corresponding to a burned area equivalent to 73% of the complex's surface, with an average fire frequency of two to three events per year (Boanha & Nhongo, 2024).

Recurrent, high-intensity fires hinder forest regeneration (Cunliffe, Mackie, & Muller, 2008), reduce the availability of forage resources, destroy habitats and microhabitats, cause mortality in low-mobility species, and threaten the livelihoods of local communities that depend directly on natural resources (ANAC, 2016; Hald-Mortensen, 2023; Clare et al., 2024). In this context, understanding the factors influencing wildfire occurrence in the Marromeu Complex is essential for informing fire management strategies and conservation actions (Chen et al., 2023).

While studies on fire regimes exist for other regions of Mozambique (Shaffer, 2010; Ribeiro et al., 2017; Nhongo et al., 2019), research specifically targeting the Marromeu Complex remains scarce (Boanha & Nhongo, 2024). Addressing this gap, the present study aims to identify the main drivers of wildfire occurrence in the Marromeu Complex, using geotechnologies and regression analysis as investigative tools.

2 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORKS

Wildfires constitute an essential process in terrestrial systems, exhibiting spatio-temporal variation that can be characterized through the concept of fire regime (Oddi, 2018). Despite its widespread use, the concept still lacks a standardized definition and is generally understood as the set of measurable parameters that describe the frequency, intensity, size, pattern, and seasonality of fires in a given ecosystem (Krebs et al., 2010; Pausas et al., 2019).

Fire regimes are controlled by climatic, topographic, biological, and anthropogenic factors that interact across multiple scales (Oddi, 2018). Among climatic factors, temperature, relative humidity, wind, and precipitation play a key role in determining ignition and fire spread (Batista, 2000; Pereira et al., 2024). Temperatures above 29.4 °C represent an extreme risk of flammability (Soares, 2003), while prolonged drought periods are strongly correlated with large fire events (Leonardo et al., 2011). Precipitation contributes to reducing fire propagation and influences atmospheric and hydrological processes in tropical regions (Soares, 2003; Yamasoe et al., 2000). Relative humidity modulates the combustion of forest fuels and tends to decrease during periods of greater solar radiation, particularly between 12:00 and 16:00 (Tamiozzo & Torres, 2006). From a topographic perspective, terrain morphology influences both fuel availability and fire dynamics. Low-altitude regions and steeper slopes exhibit higher fire

frequency, as upward fire propagation is accelerated by thermal convection (Russell-Smith et al., 2007; Batista, 2000; Jaiswal et al., 2002).

Human activity constitutes one of the main determinants of fire occurrence, being associated with accessibility to natural areas, proximity to urban centers, and road networks (Novillo, 2008). Currently, most ignitions at the global scale are caused by anthropogenic activities, particularly agriculture, hunting, and land-use expansion (Martínez, et al., 2009), which distinguish wildfires from other natural disasters (Pereira et al., 2024).

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 FIELD STUDY

The Marromeu Complex encompasses approximately 11,272 km² in central Mozambique, extending south of the Zambezi River delta and adjacent to the Cheringoma Escarpment. It comprises the Marromeu Buffalo Reserve (also designated as the Marromeu Special Reserve), two forest reserves (Nhampacué and Inhamitanga), four officially recognized hunting concessions (Coutadas Nos. 10, 11, 12, and 14), extensive sugarcane plantations operated by Açucareira de Sena, and surrounding community-managed lands (Rebelo & Beilfuss, 2010).

Geographically, the complex lies between latitudes 17° 59' 37" S and 19° 20' 32" S, and longitudes 34° 59' 23" E and 36° 11' 26" E (Fig. 1).

Figure 1

Geographic location of the field area.

3.2 DATA USED

This study employed an integrated set of environmental, topographic, socioeconomic, and vegetation variables to investigate the determinants of wildfire occurrence in the Marromeu Complex. Climatic variables included mean temperature; relative humidity; and precipitation. Topographic variables comprised altitude, slope, and solar radiation exposure. Socioeconomic factors encompassed population density and proximity to major roads. Vegetation cover was represented by the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI). Fire frequency data were derived from MODIS products MCD64A1 (burned area).

3.3 DATA ACQUISITION AND PROCESSING

Climate: Monthly temperature and precipitation data were obtained from the WorldClim v2 database (Hijmans et al., 2005) at a spatial resolution of 1 km, in raster format (Esri Grid). Temperature values ($^{\circ}\text{C} \times 10$) and precipitation values (mm/10) were converted to actual

measurements by applying the corresponding scaling factors. The datasets were clipped to the study area and aggregated into annual means. Relative humidity data were retrieved from the ERA5 reanalysis via the Climate Data Store (CDS), originally at 0.25° spatial resolution, and resampled to 500 m using nearest neighbor interpolation. Data covered the period from January 2002 to December 2019.

Topography: a 30 m resolution Digital Elevation Model (DEM) was obtained from the USGS EarthExplorer platform. From the DEM, Elevation and slope maps were derived in ArcGIS 10.8, and solar radiation exposure was calculated using the Area Solar Radiation tool. **Vegetation Cover:** NDVI was computed from Landsat 7 and 8 imagery (30 m spatial resolution, 16-day temporal resolution) acquired from the USGS GloVis portal for the period 2002–2019 (*path*:166 and 167, *row*: 073). Only cloud-free images were selected, and monthly and annual NDVI averages were calculated.

Socioeconomic Variables: Population density data were obtained from the Gridded Population of the World v4.11 dataset (CIESIN, 2018) at 1 km resolution in raster format. Road network data (highways and primary roads) were provided by CENACARTA in vector format, then rasterized and processed to compute Euclidean distance. Fire frequency was quantified by aggregating the monthly burned-area layers from the MCD64A1 product, defining frequency as the number of times each 500 m pixel was detected as burned (Archibald et al., 2010; Ribeiro et al., 2017). Each annual burned-area map was binarized (0 = unburned; 1 = burned), and these binary rasters were summed over the entire time series to yield, for every pixel, the total number of burn events (Maúnze, 2016; Ribeiro et al., 2017). Figure 2 illustrates the spatial distribution of the principal predictor variables examined in this study.

Figure 2

Spatial representation of the variables used in the study: (A) precipitation (mm); (B) temperature (°C); (C) elevation (m); (D) slope (%); (E) population density (inhabitants/km²); (F) vegetation cover (NDVI, %); (G) solar exposure (Wh/m²); (H) Roads; (I) relative humidity of the air; (J) fire frequency

3.4 STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

All independent variables (climatic, topographic, socioeconomic, and vegetation) and the dependent variable (fire frequency) were compiled in ArcGIS 10.8 and exported for statistical analysis in Python. A multiple linear regression model was fitted to quantify the relative influence of each variable on fire frequency, according to Equation 1:

$$y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \dots + \beta_n x_n + \varepsilon_i \quad (1)$$

where:

y_i = fire intensity (FRP)

x_i = the independent variables

β_i = the estimated coefficients

ε_i = the random error term

The regression model diagnostics were conducted using the *statsmodels* library, with a significance level of 5%. The objective was to verify compliance with the classical assumptions of linear regression and to identify potential issues related to bias or influential observations.

The individual significance of the estimated coefficients was assessed using the *t*-test, whereas the overall significance of the model was examined through ANOVA (*F*-test), which compares the variance explained by the regression with the residual variance (Meier et al., 2023; Viana-Soto et al., 2017; Cumming, 2001; Kountouris and Remoundou, 2011; Ma et al., 2022). Serial autocorrelation of the residuals was evaluated using the Durbin–Watson test, complemented by correlogram analysis and the Ljung–Box test (Shabbir et al., 2023; Guo et al., 2015; Viganó et al., 2018; Sharma et al., 2024). Homoscedasticity was assessed with the Breusch–Pagan test, more sensitive to outliers (Akewugberu et al., 2023), and the White test, which is more general, considering *p*-values above 0.05 as evidence of homoscedasticity (Muhammad et al., 2023).

The normality of residuals was verified using the Jarque–Bera and Shapiro–Wilk tests, confirming the adequacy of the normal distribution. Multicollinearity among explanatory variables was investigated through the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF), with values greater than 10 considered indicative of severe collinearity. Finally, the influence of individual observations was examined using Cook’s distance, leverage measures, and DFBETAs, applying cutoff criteria recommended in the literature. These procedures ensured the robustness and validity of the model prior to the interpretation of results (Siraj-Ud-Doulah, 2019; Thompson et al., 2017; Cook, 2025).

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 SEASONAL DYNAMICS OF FIRE OCCURRENCE IN THE MARROMEU COMPLEX

During the analysis period from 2002 to 2019, a consistent pattern of fire occurrence was observed throughout the year in the Marromeu Complex. Between January and March, no fires were recorded, a period typically characterized by frequent rainfall, which leads to flooding in many areas of the complex. From May to December, burned areas expanded

progressively. In May, fire occurrences were localized and limited to small, isolated spots. From June onward, these areas began to expand continuously, reflecting the intensification of the dry season. Between July and October, burned areas reached their peak, covering extensive regions within the complex, particularly in areas with dense vegetation and peat soils, where accumulated biomass significantly increases fire susceptibility (Fig. 3).

Spatially, fire fronts advanced from the northern and western boundaries toward the central and southern parts of the territory, following continuous vegetation corridors and lower-altitude areas. Zones adjacent to water channels exhibited lower fire incidence, acting as natural barriers that slow flame propagation. The decline observed in November and December coincided with the onset of rainfall, facilitating the containment of active fires and promoting progressive landscape regeneration.

Figure 3

Monthly spatial distribution of burned areas in the Marromeu Complex (May–December 2002–2019).

4.2 INFLUENCE OF ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC VARIABLES ON FIRE OCCURRENCE

To evaluate the individual contribution of each predictor to fire frequency (Fr), bivariate scatterplots were generated with simple linear regression fits (Fig. 4). The analysis revealed negative associations between Fr and precipitation, elevation, NDVI, relative humidity, and distance to roads, indicating that higher values of these variables tend to reduce fire occurrence. Conversely, population density, slope, and temperature showed positive relationships, suggesting that anthropogenic pressure, topographic steepness, and higher temperatures are key drivers of increased fire frequency. The R^2 values ranged from 0.64 (Temperature) to 0.89 (population), indicating varying degrees of fit and highlighting that some factors, particularly population density, NDVI, and altitude, provide a more robust explanation of the univariate variability in Fr.

Figure 4

Relationships between fire frequency (Fr) and environmental predictors, including simple linear regression models with corresponding equations and coefficients of determination (R^2).

The ordinary least squares (OLS) regression analysis revealed a strong explanatory performance, accounting for 97.8% of the variability in fire frequency ($R^2 = 0.978$; adjusted $R^2 = 0.977$; $F = 1039$, $p < 0.001$). Coefficient estimates demonstrated that both environmental and topographic factors significantly shape fire occurrence patterns. Positive effects were observed for slope ($\beta = 0.120$, $p < 0.001$), temperature ($\beta = 1.429$, $p < 0.001$), and population density (β

= 1.070, $p = 0.001$), indicating that steeper terrain, higher temperatures, and increased human presence tend to amplify fire frequency. NDVI ($\beta = -2.209$, $p = 0.001$) also emerged as a significant predictor, suggesting that areas with higher vegetation cover are less prone to recurrent burning, likely due to increased moisture retention and reduced flammability in dense canopies.

Conversely, precipitation ($\beta = -0.712$, $p < 0.001$), elevation ($\beta = -0.160$, $p < 0.001$), relative humidity ($\beta = -0.859$, $p < 0.001$), and proximity to roads ($\beta = -0.283$, $p < 0.001$) exhibited significant negative relationships with fire frequency, reinforcing the critical role of water availability and cooler, less accessible environments in mitigating fire occurrence. Solar radiation did not reach statistical significance and was excluded from the final model.

Variance inflation factor (VIF) diagnostics confirmed the absence of severe multicollinearity, with all predictors falling below the conventional threshold of 10. This ensures that each variable contributes unique and independent information to the model.

Overall, these results provide robust empirical evidence that climatic (temperature, precipitation, humidity), topographic (slope, elevation), ecological (NDVI), and anthropogenic (population density, accessibility) factors jointly regulate fire dynamics. The model's high explanatory power and statistically sound coefficients underscore its suitability as a predictive framework for assessing fire risk and informing management strategies in fire-prone landscapes.

The estimated parameters from the multiple linear regression are presented in Table 1. This table reports, for each predictor, the coefficient estimate, its standard error, the t-statistic, the associated p-value, and the variance inflation factor (VIF).

Table 1

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis: Coefficient Estimates, Standard Errors, t-Statistics, p-Values and Variance Inflation Factors

	Coef	Std err	t	P> t	VIF
Const	-45.117	1.509	-5.302	0.000	
Precipitation	-0.712	0.002	-4.941	0.000	3.947
Elevation	-0.160	0.002	-7.464	0.000	2.167
Slope	0.120	0.019	8.493	0.000	3.069
Population density	1.070	0.009	0.828	0.0004	1.136
NDVI	-2.209	0.0075	1.594	0.0001	3.867
Relative humidity of air	-0.859	0.013	-12.106	0.000	2.190
Roads	-0.283	0.004	-7.455	0.000	1.08
Temperature	1.429	0.002	10.88	0.000	2.586

R-Squared: 0.978 Adjusted R-squared: 0.977 F-statistic: 1039 Prob (F-statistic): 5.5e-153 Log-likelihood: -265.95 AIC:549.9 BIC: 579.6

Figure 5 illustrates the magnitude and direction of the impact of each variable in the model. Green bars indicate positive effects above zero, whereas red bars represent negative impacts below the dividing line.

Figure 5

Effects of Variables: Positive (green) vs Negative (red)

The diagnostic tests confirmed that the model adequately met the underlying statistical assumptions. The Durbin–Watson statistic (1.952) indicated the absence of significant residual autocorrelation. Tests for heteroscedasticity (Breusch–Pagan, $p = 0.322$; White, $p = 0.255$) showed no evidence of variance instability, while normality tests (Jarque–Bera, $p = 0.546$; Shapiro–Wilk, $p = 0.616$) supported the assumption of approximately normally distributed residuals. Furthermore, the maximum Cook’s distance (0.074) and leverage value (0.119) suggested the absence of unduly influential observations.

Table 2

Diagnostic test results from Multiple Linear Regression: normality, autocorrelation, heteroscedasticity, multicollinearity and influence diagnostics.

Test category	Diagnostic	Statistic	p-Value	Reference/cut-off
Normality of residuals	Omnibus	1.120	0.571	-
	Jarque-Bera (JB)	1.212	0.546	-
	Shapiro–Wilk	-	0.616	-
	Skewness	0.132	-	-
	Kurtosis	2.726	-	-
Autocorrelation of Residuals	Durbin-watson	1.952	-	≈ 2.0
Heteroscedasticity	Breusch–Pagan	-	0.3218	-
	White	-	0.2545	-
Multicollinearity	Condition number	8.172	-	< 30
Influence of Observations	Cook’s distance	0.0735	-	< 1
	Leverage	0.1191	-	$\approx (p + 1)/n$

Figure 6 presents the main diagnostic plots of the linear regression applied in this study. On the left, the histogram of residuals is overlaid with a density curve; in the center, Cook’s distance is shown with the conventional threshold of 1; and on the right, the residuals-versus-leverage plot displays the contours corresponding to Cook’s D = 0.5 and 1.

Figure 6

Diagnostic plots of the linear regression model

The histogram of residuals, overlaid with a density curve, indicated an approximately symmetric, bell-shaped distribution centered on zero, supporting the validity of inferential statistics. Cook’s distance values were all below the conventional threshold of 1, with intermediate cases remaining under 0.5, suggesting no observations exerted undue influence on model estimates. The residuals-versus-leverage plot, with contours for Cook’s D = 0.5 and D = 1, revealed no extreme cases and showed no funnel-shaped pattern, indicating homoscedasticity.

The results indicate that vegetation cover (NDVI) is the primary determinant of fire occurrence, followed by temperature, population density, relative humidity, precipitation, proximity to roads, elevation, and slope. The strong negative association between NDVI and fire occurrence aligns with findings from Nhongo et al. (2019) and Ribeiro et al. (2009), who observed higher fire incidence in areas of low vegetation density. Temperature showed a positive effect, particularly in the dry season, when reduced humidity and rainfall increase flammability, consistent with the mechanisms described by Fried et al. (2008), Tamiozzo and Torres (2006), and also reported for the Niassa Reserve (Nhongo et al., 2019). Precipitation exhibited spatially variable effects, with higher fire activity in drier areas, corroborating Soares (2003) and Archibald et al. (2010). Human activities also emerged as critical drivers, with population density and road proximity linked to ignitions associated with agriculture, charcoal production, hunting, and settlement expansion (Silva & Bento, 2006; Beilfuss, Bento, & Silva, 2010; Novillo, 2008; Finlay et al., 2012; Lasslop & Kloster, 2017; Pausas et al., 2019; Mathe, 2013). Finally, topographic effects were consistent with the literature, as slope accelerated fire spread and elevation reduced fire occurrence, highlighting the role of terrain in shaping fire dynamics (Byram, 1959; Batista, 2000; Jaiswal et al., 2002; Abbate et al., 2019; Ebel, 2012; Santos et al., 2020).

5 CONCLUSION

In the Marromeu Complex, the fire regime was predominantly shaped by vegetation cover, followed by temperature, population density, relative humidity, precipitation, proximity to roads, altitude, and slope. Vegetation cover emerged as the primary determinant, with fires occurring more frequently in sparsely vegetated areas. Population density was also a major driver, as highly populated regions experienced higher fire frequency. Climatic factors showed distinct patterns: temperature exhibited a positive relationship with fire occurrence, while precipitation and relative humidity were negatively associated. Topographic variables revealed contrasting roles, with higher elevations limiting fire spread, whereas steeper slopes facilitated it. Additionally, road proximity acted as a critical ignition factor, reflecting anthropogenic influence. The adjusted linear model demonstrated strong explanatory power, accounting for 97.8% of the observed variability ($R^2 = 0.978$; adjusted $R^2 = 0.977$). These findings highlight the pressing need to reinforce fire management strategies and environmental education initiatives in the Marromeu Complex, aiming to mitigate fire risks and safeguard ecosystem resilience.

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